

Nurses' Satisfaction and Organizational Support toward Staff Development Training Program in El-Beheira Governorate Hospitals

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Abstract: Background: Continuous training and professional development play a crucial role in the nursing profession for multiple reasons. They enable nurses to stay current with evolving healthcare practices, including updated treatment methods and advancements in medical technology. Ongoing education promotes a culture of continuous learning, which is vital for both personal advancement and career. Aim of the study: was to assess nurses' satisfaction and organizational support toward staff development training program in El-Beheira governorate hospitals. Design: A descriptive research design was utilized. Settings: Five hospitals selected to constitute 25% of the total general hospital of El-Beheira Governorate. The hospitals with the highest numbers of nurses purposefully selected namely (Itay Al-Baroud Central Hospital, Kafr El-dwar General Hospital, El Rahmnya Central Hospital, Damanhour Fever Hospital and Hosh-Esa Central). Subjects: random sample of 400 nurses was included in the current study. Tools: two tools were used Program questionnaire schedule was used in the current study which consisted of three parts: Part I): Socio-Demographic characteristics of nurse. Tool (I): Nurses' Satisfaction toward Staff Development Training. Tool (II): Perceived Organizational Support. Results: 61% of nurses were highly satisfied with the training program; while 57% of them had high level of perception of organizational support. Conclusion: it can be concluded that applying most of nurses demonstrated a high level of satisfaction this high level of satisfaction reflects the perceived effectiveness of training content, trainer characteristics, clinical procedure, and the learning environment. According to perceived organizational support, The POS was significantly influenced by variables such as age, experience, department, and hospital, indicating that workplace context and tenure shape nurses' perceptions of support. Recommendations: Continuous training programs workshops for nursing trainers and health educators based on updated and scientific based evidence according to each specialty For Healthcare organizations should more effort should establish a recognition/reward programs which include the provision of job-related benefits such as educational reimbursement, flexible scheduling, and work bonuses to decrease nurses' burnout and increasing their satisfaction

Keywords: Nurses' Satisfaction, Organizational Support, Staff development, Training Program.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern nursing encompasses numerous specialized and advanced practice roles, including nurse practitioners, clinical nurse specialists, and nurse educators or trainers. Although the profession initially focused on basic caregiving and support, it has undergone considerable transformation. This evolution underscores the rising demand for highly skilled and knowledgeable nurses who can provide competent and comprehensive care in a wide range of healthcare settings (Kurtović et al., 2024).

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Aligned with Egypt Vision 2030's emphasis on delivering high-quality healthcare, there is a growing recognition of the need for organizational support to ensure the satisfaction of healthcare workers, particularly nursing staff. In response, health directorates—such as El-Beheira Health Directorate, under the supervision of the Ministry of Health and Population—have implemented structured and standardized staff development training programs tailored to the various nursing specialties within each hospital.

These programs are designed to support nursing staff, improve their skills, and ultimately enhance patient care. This is part of a broader effort to ensure healthcare workers are supported and their satisfaction is addressed (Latif et al., 2018).

Continuous training and professional development play a crucial role in the nursing profession for multiple reasons. They enable nurses to stay current with evolving healthcare practices, including updated treatment methods and advancements in medical technology. Ongoing education promotes a culture of continuous learning, which is vital for both personal advancement and career progression. These programs also emphasize the development of both clinical competencies and interpersonal skills like effective communication and empathy that are key to providing compassionate, patient-centered care. (Aziz, 2023).

Effective nursing trainers not only deliver content but also serve as role models, inspiring nurses to uphold high standards of care and professionalism. By fostering critical thinking, encouraging continuous learning, and creating an inclusive training atmosphere, they help build a resilient and competent nursing workforce capable of meeting the evolving demands of the healthcare system (Azadian et al., 2024).

Creating a supportive work environment where nurses feel encouraged to ask questions and seek guidance is essential for their growth and development. When nursing trainers demonstrate approachability, expertise, and mentorship, they empower nurses to build confidence and enhance their clinical competence, ultimately leading to improved patient care. Positive perceptions of trainers foster open communication, teamwork, and trust, all of which are critical for effective mentorship and the success of ongoing professional development initiatives (Gottlieb et al., 2021).

Additionally, positive perceptions of trainers, along with strong organizational support, play a vital role in enhancing nurses' job satisfaction. Satisfaction with clinical training is a key component of the nursing professional experience and can greatly influence job performance, motivation, and overall well-being. Achieving a high level of satisfaction requires that nurses receive adequate and consistent support from their organizations, ensuring they have the resources, guidance, and encouragement needed to thrive in their roles (Zheng et al., 2024,).

Organizational support refers to a nurse's perception of how much their organization values their contributions and prioritizes their well-being. According to organizational support theory, when nurses feel genuinely appreciated and supported by their organization, they are more likely to demonstrate high levels of job performance. This sense of support can significantly influence workplace behaviors, including reducing absenteeism and lowering turnover intentions (Sahraian et al., 2024, Badawe et al, 2024)

However several barriers can hinder effective organizational support and clinical training for nurses in hospital settings. These obstacles include organizational constraints such as insufficient resources, heavy workloads, and inadequate staffing. Patient related challenges such as limited case variety or patient reluctance to participate in care activities can also impact training quality. Additionally, negative attitudes toward nurses, unengaged or ineffective trainers, and a lack of organizational commitment can contribute to dissatisfaction. These issues could lead to a higher rate of nurse turnover and compromise the continuity and standard of patient care (Alqahtani et al., 2022; Alsadaan & Ramadan, 2025; Mostafa, Harfoush et al .. 2025).

Although many studies have investigated nurses' satisfaction and organizational support, there is a lack of research that specifically measures nurses' satisfaction and organizational support in Egypt. So, this study wishes to assess the nurses' satisfaction and organizational support toward the training programs at hospitals in the El-Beheira governorate.

The aim of this study was to:

Assess nurses' satisfaction and organizational support toward staff development training program in El-Beheira governorate hospitals.

Research questions:

1. What are nurses' levels of satisfaction toward staff development training program in El-Beheira governorate hospitals?
2. What are nurses' levels of perception about organizational support toward staff development training programs in El-Beheira governorate hospitals?

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research design:

A descriptive research design was utilized to conduct this study.

Study settings:

The study was carried out at hospitals in El-Beheira Governorate distributed as twenty general and six health centers providing all healthcare services for the population. Five hospitals selected to constitute 25% of the total general hospital of El-Beheira Governorate. The hospitals with the highest numbers of nurses purposefully selected namely (Itay Al-Baroud Central Hospital, Kafr El-dwar General Hospital, El Rahmnya Central Hospital, Damanhour Fever Hospital and Hosh-Esa Central).

Study subjects:

Random sample from the five mentioned hospitals was taken based on statistics. It included 400 nursing staff selected randomly from the five mentioned hospitals.

Tools of the study:

Two tools were used in this study for data collection.

Tool (I):- “Nurses’ Satisfaction toward Staff Development Training Program Questionnaire”

This tool was developed by the researcher after an extensive review of the literature (Knox & Mogan, 1985; Hsu et al., 2014) and translated into Arabic to assess nurses' satisfaction toward the training program. It consisted of four dimensions which included thirty-five statements. The first dimension is the trainer characteristics which included fifteen statements, the second dimension is the content which included ten statements, the third dimension is the clinical procedures which included 5 statements and the fourth dimension is the training environment which included five statements.

The overall score of nurses' satisfactions was calculated in percentages as follow: - low satisfaction represented a score of less than 50%, moderate satisfaction represented from 50 to less than 75% and high satisfaction represented more than 75%.

In addition to, personal and professional work-related data of nurses which included nurse's age, gender, residence, academic qualification, hospital name, department, years of experience ... etc.

Tool (II): Perceived Organizational Support:

This tool was developed by the researcher after an extensive review of the literatures (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Bjarnason, 2009; Zeb et al., 2019; Tjoa & Arief, 2021) and translated into Arabic to assess nurses' level of perception about their organizational support. which included 21 statements.

The overall score of nurses perceived organizational support was calculated in percentages as follow: - low perception represented a score of less than 50%, moderate perception represented a score from 50 to less than 75% and high perception represented a score above 75%.

Validity & Reliability:

- The two tools were developed and translated into Arabic and tested for its content validity by a panel of five experts in the field of Nursing Education and Nursing administration at the faculty of Nursing Damanhour University. The necessary modifications were done accordingly

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- A pilot study was carried out on (10%) of the total population approximately, (n=40) nursing staff to test the clarity and applicability of the study tool and identify obstacles and problems that may be encountered during data collection. Those participants were excluded from the actual study. The pilot study proved that the study tools were clear and feasible.
- The two tools were tested for their reliability by using Cronbach's alpha correlation coefficient test to measure the internal consistency of items. The two tools were proved to be reliable with a value= 0.965 for tool I (Nurses' Satisfaction toward Staff Development Training Program) and a value =0.976 for tool II (Perceived Organizational Support).

Fieldwork:

- Data was collected by interviewing with nurses who agreed to participate in the study. As the researcher interview (20-25) nurses daily according to distribution of the sample size in each hospital. Each hospital was visited from 2 to three times per week based on sample size. The time required to complete the questionnaires was approximately 10-15 minutes after providing a detailed explanation of the study's objectives.
- The data collection phase spanned two months, commencing from the beginning of January and concluding at the end of February 2025.

Ethical considerations

- Research ethical approval was obtained from the Research Ethical Committee (REC) at the Faculty of Nursing, Damanhour University, prior to the start of the study.
- A written informed consent was obtained from the study subjects after explanation the aim of the study.
- Confidentiality and anonymity of data were maintained during implementation of the study.
- Right to refuse to participate or withdraw from the study at any time was ensured during the study.

Statistical Analysis:

After data were collected it was revised, coded, and fed to statistical software IBM SPSS version 25. The reliability of the tools was determined by Cronbach's alpha. Frequency tables and cross-tabulation were used to illustrate the results. Quantitative data were summarized by the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and mean score percent. All statistical analysis was done using two-tailed tests and an alpha error of 0.05. A P-value less than or equal to 0.05 was considered to be statistically significant.

III. RESULTS

Table (1) shows distribution of the nurses in relation to their personal and professional work related data.

It was found that age, it was observed that less than half (42.3%) of nurses were between 30 to 40 years old and the majority (89.2%) of nurses were female and only 10.8% were male. Additionally more than half of nurses (62.5%) were from urban. Regarding educational qualification, nearly one-third (31.5%) of them had Bachelor of Nursing Science, while only 1.0% had Master degree. Concerning the years of experience, results revealed that more than two-thirds (72.3%) of nurses worked more than 5 years, while about one-third (27.7%) of them worked from 1 to 5 years.

Table (2) shows distribution of nurses according to overall nurse's satisfaction of training program.

It was found that (1.5%) of nurses had low level of satisfaction, while more than one third (37%) of them had a moderate level of satisfaction and the majority (61.5%) of them were highly satisfied with the training program

Table (3) shows distribution of nurses according to total, percent score of overall perception of perceived organizational support. It was noticed that 8.25% of nurses had low perception level, while 34% had moderate perception level and 57% of them had high level of organizational support

Table (4) presents data about the relationship between nurses' satisfaction regarding training program and their personal and professional work related data.

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It was found that there were statically significant relationship between nurses’ age, gender, years of experience, hospital name and department and their levels of satisfaction regarding training program where p values were (0.001*,0.008*,0.020*0.000* and 0.000*) respectively. While there were no statically significant relationship between nurses’ residence and educational qualification their levels of satisfaction regarding training program where p values were (0.827 and 0.191) respectively.

Table (5) presents data about the relationship between nurses’ perception of Perceived organizational support and their personal and professional work related data.

It was found that there were statically significant relationship between between nurses’ age, gender, years of experience, hospital name and department and their levels of perceived organizational support Where p values were (0.000*,0.001*,0.005*,0.000*and 0.001*) respectively. While there were no statically significant relationship between nurses’ residence and educational qualification their levels of perceived organizational support where p values were (0.593 and 0.161) respectively.

Table (6): Correlation between the nursing staff levels of overall satisfaction and organizational support:

Table (6) shows the correlation between the overall nurses satisfaction and the overall perceived organizational support as well as the inter correlation between various training dimension.

There was a significant positive correlation between the four training program dimension (p=0.000). These results suggest the improvement in one training dimension is likely associated and resulted in improvement in the other dimension. Consequently there was a very strong positive correlation between satisfaction and other four dimension the trainer personal characteristics, the clinical procedure, the training environment and the content with R=1, 0.715**,0.613** and 0.695** respectively. All these correlation are highly significant P=0.000 these indicates that satisfaction is strongly influenced by the four dimension. regarding POS, it was also positive correlation with all training dimension (the trainer personal characteristics, the clinical procedure, The training environment and the content) with R=0.497**, 0.578**,0.632** and 0.638** respectively. Which show that POS has lower degree than satisfaction. Finally, these findings suggest that improving four dimension is likely enhance both nurses satisfaction and the perception of organizational support

Table (1): Distribution of the nurses according to their personal and professional work related data (N=400)

personal and professional work related data		N =400	%
1	Age		
	▪ 21-<30	152	38.0
	▪ 30-<40	169	42.3
	▪ 40-<50	52	13.0
	▪ 50-<60	27	6.7
2	Gender		
	▪ male	43	10.8
	▪ female	357	89.2
3	Residence		
	▪ Rural	150	37.5
	▪ Urban	250	62.5
4	Educational qualification		
	▪ Secondary Nursing School diploma	106	26.5
	▪ Technical nursing Institute Diploma	106	26.5
	▪ Bachelor of nursing science	126	31.5
	▪ Diploma degree	58	14.5
	▪ Master degree	4	1.0
5	Years of experience		
	▪ 1-< 5 years	111	27.7
	▪ >5 years	289	72.3
6	Hospital name		
	▪ Itay Al-Baroud Hospital	150	37.5
	▪ Kafr El-Dawar Hospital	82	20.5

personal and professional work related data		N =400	%
	▪ El Rahmnya Hospital	63	15.8
	▪ Damnhou Fever Hospital	50	12.5
	▪ Hosh-Esa Hospital	55	13.7
7	Department		
	▪ Reception	39	9.7
	▪ Internal Departments	88	22.0
	▪ Nursery	26	6.5
	▪ Insolation	6	1.5
	▪ Orthopedic	4	1.0
	▪ Operations	12	3.0
	▪ General Care	73	18.3
	▪ Clinics	27	6.8
	▪ Kidney	33	8.3
	▪ Baby Care	39	9.8
	▪ Poison Care	14	3.5
	▪ Cardiac Care	13	3.2
	▪ Surgery Department	13	3.2
	▪ burn Department	7	1.7
▪ Toxicology Department	6	1.5	

Table (2):Distribution of nurses according to their overall satisfaction regarding the training program: (N=400)

Overall satisfaction of nurses in relation to training program	N	%
Low Nurses satisfaction (< 50%)	6	1.50%
Moderate Nurses satisfaction (50 % <75%)	148	37.00%
High Nurses satisfaction (≥ 75 %)	246	61.50%
Total Score		
Min- Max	47.0 -140.0	
Mean ± SD	105.10±12.88	
Percent Score		
Min- Max	33.57 – 100	
Mean ± SD	75.07±9.20	

Table (3):Distribution nurses according to their overall levels of organizational support (N=400)

Overall perception of perceived organizational support	N	%
Low perception (< 50%)	33	8.25%
Moderate perception ((50 % < 75%))	139	34.75%
High perception ((≥ 75 %))	228	57.00%
Total Score		
Min- Max	21.0 -84.0	
Mean±SD	59.56±11.63	
Percent Score		
Min- Max	25.0 - 100	
Mean±SD	70.91±13.85	

Table (4): Relationship between nursing staff personal and professional work related data and their levels of satisfaction regarding the training program

personal and professional work related data	Nurses' Satisfaction
	Mean ± SD.
Age	
▪ 21-<30	102.65±12.20
▪ 30-<40	105.15±13.37
▪ 40-<50	110.02±13.34
▪ 50-<60	109.04±8.75
Test of sig.(p)	F=5.373(0.001)*
Gender	
▪ Male	110.00±12.43
▪ Female	104.50±12.82
Test of sig.(p)	T=2.664(0.008)*
Residence	
▪ Rural	104.91±13.01
▪ Urban	105.20±12.82
Test of sig.(p)	T=0.218(0.827)
Educational qualification	
▪ Secondary Nursing School diploma	107.09±12.33
▪ Technical nursing Institute Diploma	104.94±12.82
▪ Bachelor of nursing science	104.06±12.20
▪ Diploma degree	103.38±15.16
▪ Master degree	113.50±8.70
Test of sig.(p)	F=1.536(0.191)
Years of experience	
▪ 1-< 5 years	102.68±11.75
▪ >5 years	106.02±13.19
Test of sig.(p)	T=2.341(0.020)*
Hospital name	
▪ Itay Al-Baroud Hospital	99.76±13.35
▪ Kafr El-Dawar Hospital	104.17±14.79
▪ El Rahmnya Hospital	104.75±7.39
▪ Damnhou Fever Hospital	112.74±5.85
▪ Hosh-Esa Hospital	114.47±9.39
Test of sig.(p)	F=22.108(0.000)*
Department	
▪ Reception	102.92±13.23
▪ Internal Departments	105.42±15.17
▪ Nursery	103.62±9.82
▪ Insolation	112.33±7.63
▪ Orthopedic	103.00±1.15
▪ Operations	111.00±8.95
▪ General Care	102.96±13.22
▪ Clinics	116.26±13.35
▪ Kidney	106.48±8.78
▪ Baby Care	100.36±10.79
▪ Poison Care	104.36±9.60
▪ Cardiac Care	104.54±15.40
▪ Surgery Department	99.00±7.84
▪ Burn Department	110.57±5.80
▪ Toxicology Department	111.83±6.46
Test of sig.(p)	F=3.054(0.000)*

T: Independent Samples Test F: One Way ANOVA

Table (5): Relationship between nursing staff personal and professional work related data and their levels of organizational support

personal and professional work related data	Perceived Organizational Support Scale (POSS)
	Mean ± SD.
Age	
21-<30	56.75±12.47
30-<40	60.37±11.01
40-<50	63.23±10.88
50-<60	63.30±8.17
Test of sig.(p)	F=6.106(0.000)*
Gender	
Male	65.21±9.32
Female	58.88±11.71
Test of sig.(p)	T=3.414(0.001)*
Residence	
Rural	59.16±12.67
Urban	59.80±10.99
Test of sig.(p)	T=0.535(0.593)
Educational qualification	
Secondary Nursing School diploma	61.45±11.24
Technical nursing Institute Diploma	59.57±11.20
Bachelor of nursing science	58.73±11.75
Diploma degree	57.47±12.83
Master degree	66.00±2.94
Test of sig.(p)	F=1.649(0.161)
Years of experience	
1-< 5 years	56.95±12.48
>5 years	60.57±11.15
Test of sig.(p)	T=2.812(0.005)*
Hospital name	
Itay Al-Baroud Hospital	55.35±12.61
Kafr El-Dawar Hospital	59.40±9.41
El Rahmnya Hospital	55.59±12.03
Damnhou Fever Hospital	68.36±4.19
Hosh-Esa Hospital	67.85±6.09
Test of sig.(p)	F=26.172(0.000)*
Department	
Reception	57.15±11.92
Internal Departments	61.17±10.95
Nursery	57.19±12.77
Insolation	66.67±3.27
Orthopedic	63.00±0.00
Operations	65.33±6.93
General Care	58.92±11.58
Clinics	63.11±9.97
Kidney	61.09±10.39
Baby Care	51.97±15.88
Poison Care	58.43±6.51
Cardiac Care	60.54±12.68
Surgery Department	58.54±5.47
burn Department	68.14±4.71
Toxicology Department	66.50±8.89
Test of sig.(p)	F=2.738(0.001)*

T: Independent Samples Test

F: One Way ANOVA

Table (6): Correlation between the nursing staff levels of overall satisfaction and organizational support

Dimensions		In relation to the trainer personal characteristics	In relation to the clinical procedure	The training environment	In relation to the content	Nurses' Satisfaction	Perceived Organizational Support Scale (POSS)
In relation to the trainer personal characteristics	R	1					
	P						
In relation to the clinical procedure	R	0.715**	1				
	P	0.000					
The training environment	R	0.613**	0.649**	1			
	P	0.000	0.000				
In relation to the content	R	0.695**	0.740**	0.699**	1		
	P	0.000	0.000	0.000			
Nurses' Satisfaction	R	0.909**	0.856**	0.804**	0.901**	1	
	P	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000		
Perceived Organizational Support Scale (POSS)	R	0.497**	0.578**	0.632**	0.638**	0.651**	1
	P	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

* Pearson correlation test

IV. DISCUSSION

Effective nursing trainers play a pivotal role in empowering nurses, improving competencies, and fostering a culture of trust and mentorship. Moreover, positive perceptions of trainers and strong organizational support directly influence nurses' satisfaction, retention, and performance, ultimately leading to better patient outcomes (Kim & Cho, 2022).

In the present study, the researcher evaluated nurses' satisfaction and organizational support toward staff development training program in El-Beheira governorate hospitals. In this essence, the researcher will discuss the findings initially with personal professional work related.

The study findings regarding the personal and professional work related data of nurses they were as follow; the present study showed that nearly half of the nurses were between 30 to 40 years old, indicating a mid-career workforce. This may be attributed to age group was generally seen as professionally mature and more receptive to reflective learning and skills improvement. The dominance of mid-career nurses in the current study may suggest reduced demand for entry-level training but a higher expectation for specialized, practical, and leadership-oriented development.

This finding is aligned with Kim and Cho (2022), who found that support programs were particularly effective among nurses in their 30s, as this group often seeks growth, stability, and professional recognition. These nurses are also more likely to balance clinical competence with openness to new organizational initiatives. This result is in congruent also with Fawaz et al. (2021) study, which revealed that novice nurses under 30 years old, although less in number, exhibited a higher need for structured guidance and onboarding support.

The current study showed that more than half of nurses were from urban areas. This may be attributed to better access to training resources, technology, and supportive infrastructure. Urban nurses typically have more exposure to updated protocols, continuing education, and institutional support. The urban-heavy sample in the current study may imply a training reach gap and highlights the importance of extending future programs to underserved rural hospitals to ensure equity in nurse development across regions.

This finding is aligned with Suprpto et al. (2023), who emphasized that nurses from urban areas exhibit higher satisfaction due to stronger human resources development systems. This result also aligned with Walker (2018), who highlighted that rural nurses often experience feelings of professional isolation and are underrepresented in training opportunities.

The present study revealed that nearly one-third of nurses had Bachelor of nursing science; a significant portion came from technical or secondary nursing education backgrounds. This result may be due to suggest varying levels of preparedness and expectations from training sessions. This result is agreement with Ahmad et al. (2022), who found that higher educational levels correlate with greater demand for evidence-based practice, autonomy, and leadership development.

This result is conversely with Chiampou et al. (2024), who found that nurses with lower formal qualifications may demonstrate strong organizational commitment if they perceive training as accessible and empowering. The mixed educational profile in the study underscores the need to design stratified training programs that are inclusive of different learning needs and knowledge baselines.

The current study showed that more than two-thirds of nurses worked more than 5 years of experience, this result could be due to the workforce can be described as experienced and potentially settled in their professional roles. Experienced nurses are often expected to mentor others, lead clinical initiatives, and benefit from advanced professional development. This result is in harmony with Ibrahim et al. (2021) study, which confirmed that longer tenure is associated with higher job commitment when organizational support and professional development are present. In addition to, Rawashdeh and Tamimi (2020) study, warned that nurses with fewer years of experience are more vulnerable to turnover intentions when training and organizational support are lacking.

As regard overall levels of satisfaction, the study revealed that the majority of nurses demonstrated a high level of satisfaction, more than one-third of nurses moderately satisfied, and few of nurses reporting low satisfaction. This high level of satisfaction reflects the perceived effectiveness of training content, trainer characteristics, clinical demonstrations, and the learning environment

This result is consistent with Kim and Cho (2022) who found that well-designed nurse support and training programs significantly improve job satisfaction and organizational behaviors.

High satisfaction levels also have broader implications for organizational commitment and retention. These results align with international benchmarks of successful training programs in healthcare, where majority of nurses reported high satisfaction rate is typical of well-received interventions. However, King et al. (2021) cautioned that satisfaction should not be the only metric for success. Evaluators must also assess training impact on performance, patient outcomes, and long-term knowledge retention.

According to Rawashdeh and Tamimi (2020), when nurses perceive training as relevant, engaging, and supportive, they are more likely to remain committed to their institutions and exhibit lower turnover intentions. This may explain why the current findings show very few nurses reporting low satisfaction, as the majority saw tangible value in the program. This group may have experienced gaps in specific training dimensions such as interactive content, availability of multimedia tools, or access to updated scientific materials. Suprpto et al. (2023) Found that even well-structured training programs must continuously evolve to address nurses' growing expectations, including personalization, digitalization, and practical applications.

Concerning overall perception of perceived organizational support: The findings showed that about more than half of nurses had a high level of POS, one-third of nurses had a moderate level, and few of nurses reported a low level. The POS was significantly influenced by variables such as age, experience, department, and hospital, indicating that workplace context and tenure shape nurses' perceptions of support. While many nurses agreed that the organization provided opportunities for advancement and responded to their needs and values, about one-fifth expressed dissatisfaction regarding recognition, workload management, and incentive provision.

This result is consistent with the outcomes of Kim and Cho (2022) that found that high levels of POS are significantly associated with increased job satisfaction, organizational citizenship behaviors, and reduced turnover intention. The high proportion of nurses who perceive their institutions as supportive likely reflects the presence of development programs, responsive leadership, and structured training opportunities. These results also are supported by Baset and Karim (2020) who found that perceived support and career development opportunities significantly influence work engagement and organizational commitment.

However, the presence of one-third of nurses had moderate perception indicates areas requiring further development, such as clearer reward systems, equitable distribution of training, and improved feedback mechanisms. As emphasized by Eweida (2025), and Ahmad et al. (2022), moderate levels of POS can translate into uncertainty, where nurses feel partially supported but remain hesitant about long-term commitment or voice concerns about recognition and workload.

Regarding relationship between nurses' level of satisfaction with the training program and personal and professional work related data; there was a statistically significant relationship between nurses' level of satisfaction with the training program and several personal and academic factors, including age, gender and years of experience, hospital name, and department. These findings suggest that nurses' background and workplace setting substantially influence how they perceive the adequacy of the training environment. For example, more experienced nurses may have higher expectations for environmental quality based on previous training exposures, while younger or less experienced nurses may be more adaptable.

This aligns with Rawashdeh and Tamimi (2020), who found that early-career nurses tend to focus on access and opportunity, whereas senior nurses are more critical of logistics, ergonomics, and resources. Furthermore, differences in hospital name and department may reflect disparities in infrastructure, space, ventilation, and technology availability—factors that directly shape satisfaction with the training environment. Cheng et al. (2020) Similarly observed that tertiary hospitals tend to provide superior training environments compared to peripheral or rural institutions.

The study also revealed no statistically significant relationship between satisfaction and residence (urban or rural) or educational qualification. This suggests that the perceived quality of the training environment transcends geographical origin or academic background, indicating that physical conditions, accessibility, and delivery are more impactful than personal education or location. Yu et al. (2022) noted that regardless of prior education, nurses generally value a well-equipped and physically comfortable environment for effective learning, especially when practical skill re-demonstration is involved.

Furthermore, no significant relationship was found between POS and the nurses' residence (urban/rural) or educational qualification. Which suggests that regardless of whether a nurse comes from a rural or urban area or holds a basic or advanced qualification; their perception of organizational support is more heavily influenced by institutional behavior and direct workplace experience than by background or credentials. These findings are supported by Polat and Terzi (2021), who concluded that the key drivers of POS are rooted in how nurses are treated within the work setting through policy, communication, recognition, and workload management rather than their origin or academic standing.

The data also support the conclusions of Kurtessis et al. (2015), who established in a meta-analysis that perceived organizational support acts as a mediator between workplace practices (like training and recognition) and outcomes such as job satisfaction, performance, and retention. Thus, investments in training quality are multiplier strategies benefiting individual nurse development while also boosting institutional cohesion and morale.

Moreover, the positive correlation between training satisfaction and POS suggests that when training programs are well-executed, nurses perceive their organizations as more supportive, echoing the findings of Tjoa and Arief (2021), who linked job fit and support with positive organizational behaviors.

Champou et al. (2024) Further noted that sustained satisfaction depends not just on the program itself but also on the long-term institutional support that follows including access to continuing education, recognition systems, and growth pathways.

Finally we can conclude that this study results present a clear and statistically significant positive correlation between overall nurses' satisfaction with the training program and their POS across all measured dimensions. This strong relationship suggests that when one dimension of the training improves such as trainer effectiveness, clinical procedures, training content, or environment, there is a simultaneous increase in both overall satisfaction and POS among nurses.

These findings reinforce the interconnected nature of workplace learning and support systems. When training is delivered effectively in a well-equipped, comfortable environment, and guided by competent trainers, nurses are more likely to perceive their organization as supportive and invested in their professional development. This aligns with Kim and Cho (2022), who found that structured nurse support programs not only enhance clinical competence and satisfaction but also improve organizational loyalty and workplace climate.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

From the present study, it can be concluded that:

Applying most of nurses demonstrated a high level of satisfaction, more of nurses moderately satisfied, and few of nurses reporting low satisfaction. This high level of satisfaction reflects the perceived effectiveness of training content, trainer characteristics, clinical procedure, and the learning environment. According to perceived organizational support, that more than half of nurses had a high level of POS, one-third of nurses had a moderate level, and few of nurses reported a low level. The POS was significantly influenced by variables such as age, experience, department, and hospital, indicating that workplace context and tenure shape nurses' perceptions of support.

Based on the current study findings:

For the nurse educator:

- Continuous training programs workshops for nursing trainers and health educators based on updated and scientific based evidence according to each specialty and communication skills principles about:-
- the integration of technology and AI in teaching methods during training sessions
- problem solving and clinical judgment skills to provide appropriate decisions

For nurses:

- Continuous learning programs to improve their knowledge, work quality, and patient satisfaction.
- Participate in seminars and conferences to improve their nursing knowledge, and nursing practice.

Recommendations for future studies:

- Replicate of the study on a larger probability sample is highly recommended to generalize the results.
- Assess the supportive leadership as a mediator between occupational stress and psychological capital among nurses.

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